

CASE REPORT

Giant Chorioangioma of Placenta

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ABSTRACT

Chorioangiomas are rare benign tumors of the placenta, characterized by atrio- venous shunting within placenta leading to foetal anemia, cardiomegaly and hydrops. Maternal complications can be polyhydramnios, antepartum haemorrhage and Mirror syndrome. They are usually seen after 20 weeks, and most of them remain small and are asymptomatic. Large ones (> 4 cm) are termed as Giant Chorioangioma and can lead to foetal and maternal complications.

The proximity of the chorioangioma to the placental cord insertion site and its size determines its prognosis. Prenatal therapy in the form of interventions like direct injections of various chemicals and laser coagulation of the feeding vessels of the tumor can be done to reduce the foetal and maternal complications of giant chorioangiomas. Conservative management is done in cases of small chorioangiomas. We report a case of 27 year old female presented to us with history of 8 month amenorrhea for routine antenatal ultrasound examination and diagnosed as a case of Giant Chorioangioma. Early diagnosis was made followed by close surveillance with PSV of Doppler of MCA was done for foetal wellbeing and patient was managed conservatively with counseling of patient for any foetal and maternal complications.

INTRODUCTION

Placental chorioangioma also known as placental haemangioma is a non-trophoblastic benign tumor of the placenta that is characteristically vascular and originates from primitive chorionic tissue. It is rare and occurs in less than 1% of all pregnancies while incidence of Giant Chorioangioma is one in 9000 to one in 50000 pregnancies. Three types are recognized as Angiomatoid: characterized by numerous blood vessels, Cellular: with poor vascularisation and Degenerative: with degenerative changes.¹

Placental chorioangiomas tend to occur on the foetal side of the placenta and close to cord insertion. Small sized less than 4 cm chorioangiomas are nonsignificant. Giant Chorioangiomas are larger than 4 cm in size and increases the risk of both foetal and maternal complications. Maternal complications can be preterm labour, placental abruption, polyhydramnios, and foetal complications can be foetal hydrops, intrauterine growth restriction, foetal anaemia, cardiac failure, and even foetal demise can occur in Giant chorioangiomas. Perinatal mortality has been reported in about 30-40% cases in Giant Chorioangioma. Therefore, prenatal diagnosis is vital to follow up these pregnancies diligently.²

CASE REPORT

A 27 year old G2P1, women with a previous full term normal vaginal delivery came for routine antenatal ultrasound examination at 8 month of amenorrhea. Her previous antenatal scan in first trimester and other blood investigations were normal. There was no significant family history of any placental or foetal anomaly. On ultrasound a well defined homogenous hypoechoic mass lesion of 11 x 8 cm size with few internal cystic areas was seen arising from foetal surface of placenta and projecting into the amniotic cavity showing mild vascularity with low resistant pulsatile flow on colour doppler. Other findings were foetal cardiomegaly with dilated right atria and backflow of blood in right atrium during ventricular contraction with regurgitation velocity more than 80cm suggestive of tricuspid regurgitation. Foetal complications like mild foetal ascites were noted. There were no maternal complications. This case was diagnosed as cellular type of Giant Chorioangioma.

DISCUSSION

Placental chorioangioma is the most common benign tumor of the placenta with reported incidence of approximately 1% of all pregnancies while incidence of

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Giant Chorioangioma is one in 9000 to one in 50000 pregnancies. Most Chorioangiomas are small and asymptomatic. Large tumors more than 45 cm are associated with maternal and foetal complications. The pathophysiology of the complications is not fully understood. The main hypotheses are: chronic arterio-venous malformation with a development of a high output foetal cardiac failure and the sequestration of red blood cells and platelets within the tumor. Antenatally it is diagnosed by ultrasound as a hypo or hyperechoic rounded mass with anechoic spaces which protrude into the amniotic cavity³. Most of them are located near the umbilical cord insertion. Color Doppler displays presence of vascular channels in the tumor contiguous with the foetal circulation. The most common 14-28% fetal complications are polyhydramnios, others are preterm delivery, non-immune hydrops, fetal cardiomegaly, fetal heart failure, fetal anemia, thrombocytopenia, fetal growth retardation and intrauterine fetal demise⁴. The maternal complications include pre-eclampsia and maternal mirror syndrome (maternal edema associated to foetal hydrops). The chorioangioma is usually managed conservatively⁵. Patients are monitored by ultrasound, where foetal growth, Doppler examination, signs of hydrops and tumor size are assessed. The most common invasive therapeutic procedures are amniocentesis and intrauterine fetal blood transfusion. Other invasive interventions to block AV shunting include alcohol injection, micro coil embolisation and endoscopic laser coagulation. These techniques are more successful when tumor is located away from umbilical cord site and its circulation is not directly depended on the umbilical cord⁶.

CONCLUSION

Placental chorioangioma is certainly the most common benign tumor of placenta. Early diagnosis of placental tumor, its placental location, its composition and size of tumor with vascularity helps in reaching the final diagnosis of Giant chorioangioma. Regular ultrasound monitoring of foetal and maternal complications of Giant Chorioangiomas helps in timely intervention and thereby improving the prognosis.

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig 1 On USG a well defined homogenous hypoechoic sub chorionic mass lesion on foetal side of placenta with few internal cystic areas (A), showing vascularity (B) and low resistant pulsatile flow on colour doppler represent enlarged vascular channels (C) with mild foetal ascites (D), increased cardiothoracic ratio represent cardiomegaly (E), backflow of blood in right atrium during ventricular contraction with regurgitation velocity more than 80cm suggestive of tricuspid regurgitation.

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